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“JASPER JONES” AS NEW LIFE GIVEN TO THE NOVEL “TO KILL A MOCKINGBIRD”

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Abstract: Today, authors of masterpieces are motivated by their favorite novels they have read. In rare cases, combining several novels can result in the creation of a new one. In this context, classic literature from the twentieth century has had a significant influence on novels from the twenty-first century. One of the most striking examples is Harper Lee's *To Kill a Mockingbird* (1960), reincarnated in Craig Silvey's *Jasper Jones* (2009). Both are coming-of-age tales that address racial injustice as well as moral and mental growth. Furthermore, they depict small-town settings in which characters such as Arthur “Boo” Radley and Tom Robinson in *To Kill a Mockingbird*, and Jasper Jones and Jack Lionel in *Jasper Jones*, are misunderstood due to societal prejudice.

Key words: interconnection, racism, resemblance, coming-of-age, reappearance.

Annotatsiya: Bugungi kunda shoh asarlar mualliflari o'zlari o'qigan sevimli romanlardan ilhom oladilar. Ba'zan bir nechta romanlarning uyg'unlashuvi yangi asar yaratilishiga olib kelishi mumkin. Xususan, XX asr mumtoz adabiyoti XXI asr romanchiligiga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatgan. Buning eng yorqin misollaridan biri – Xarper Lining *Masxarabozni o'ldirish* (1960) asari bo'lib, u Kreyg Silvining *Jasper Jons* (2009) romanida qayta hayot topdi. Har ikkala asar ham voyaga yetish, irqiy adolatsizlik hamda axloqiy va ma'naviy kamolot mavzularini yoritadi. Bundan tashqari, ular kichik shahar muhitini tasvirlaydi. Bu muhitda *Masxarabozni o'ldirish* asaridagi Artur “Bu” Redli va Tom Robinson hamda *Jasper Jons*dagi Jasper Jons va Jek Lionel kabi qahramonlar jamiyatdagi noto'g'ri qarashlar tufayli noto'g'ri talqin qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: o'zaro bog'liqlik, irqchilik, o'xshashlik, voyaga yetish, qayta namoyon bo'lish.

Аннотация: Сегодня авторы шедевров вдохновляются своими любимыми прочитанными романами. В редких случаях сочетание нескольких романов может привести к созданию нового произведения. В данном контексте классическая литература XX века оказала значительное влияние на романы XXI века. Одним из самых ярких примеров является *Убить пересмешника* Харпер Ли (1960), воплощенный в новом облике в романе *Джаспер Джонс* Крейга Силви (2009). Оба произведения являются историями взросления, затрагивающими темы расовой несправедливости, а также нравственного и умственного развития. Кроме того, они изображают обстановку маленьких городков, где персонажи, такие как Артур “Страшила” Рэдли и Том Робинсон в *Убить пересмешника*, а также Джаспер Джонс и Джек Лайонел в *Джаспер Джонс*, неправильно воспринимаются обществом из-за предрассудков.

Ключевые слова: взаимосвязь, расизм, сходство, взросление, возрождение.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, authors of masterpieces are inspired by their favorite novels they have read. In some cases, combining several novels can lead to the creation of a new one. In this context, twentieth-century classic literature has often influenced the novels of the twenty-first century. One of the most remarkable examples is *To Kill a Mockingbird* by Harper Lee (1960), reborn in *Jasper Jones* by Craig Silvey (2009). Both of them are coming-of-age novels that deal with racial injustice, as well as moral and mental growth.

To Kill a Mockingbird by Harper Lee, long considered an American classic and one of the most beloved books for adolescents, has raised much controversy since its publication in 1960. It has been acknowledged as one of the most important novels of the twentieth century, and its author was presented with the Presidential Medal of Freedom in 2007 (Machala, 2023). Moreover, it portrays small-town settings where, due to societal prejudice, characters such as Arthur “Boo” Radley and Tom Robinson in *To Kill a Mockingbird*, as well as Jasper Jones and Jack Lionel in *Jasper Jones*, are misunderstood.

As mentioned by Anna Vallen in the magazine *Australian Geographies*, out of the twelve most popular and must-read novels that every Australian should read, *Jasper Jones* is listed as the tenth. She also noted that

Jasper Jones has been called “Australia’s To Kill a Mockingbird,” and that there are certainly parallel simmering tensions over one summer in the 1960s in a small town in Western Australia (2016). Even though time flows, the heroes of masterpieces live on forever and reappear in other novels. This article demonstrates this through contextual analysis by emphasizing similarities, differences, and intertextual connections between To Kill a Mockingbird by Harper Lee and Jasper Jones by Craig Silvey.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

The novel To Kill a Mockingbird by Harper Lee has been the subject of extensive scholarly analysis. Machala emphasizes its enduring relevance across generations, highlighting its influence even in modern adaptations such as graphic novels. Scholars consistently recognize the novel’s significant contribution to discussions on racial injustice, moral development, and the complexity of societal prejudice.

In the context of intertextuality, Jasper Jones by Craig Silvey is often considered a contemporary narrative that echoes themes introduced by Lee. Vellen lists Jasper Jones among the twelve essential Australian novels, noting its parallels with Lee’s work in addressing systemic racism and social exclusion within small-town settings.

Akhrorova provides specific analyses of character vulnerabilities and moral dilemmas in both novels. Her studies on Jean Louise “Scout” Finch and Tom Robinson explore how innocence, injustice, and moral conflict are central to Lee’s narrative structure and reappear in Silvey’s reinterpretation. The character arcs of Jasper Jones and Jack Lionel mirror those of Tom Robinson and Boo Radley, reinforcing shared thematic concerns.

Lee’s original portrayal of Southern American racial tensions remains a powerful foundation for comparative studies. The intergenerational transmission of these themes demonstrates the continuing cultural and pedagogical importance of both novels in literary scholarship.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This article employs a qualitative research method based on contextual analysis. By dividing the two novels into smaller segments, it analyzes the contextual similarities and the reappearance of the main characters within each work, while also identifying differences in tone, setting, and circumstances. Each novel is examined through its intertextual features. According to the research findings, Jasper Jones shares numerous similarities and differences with the novel To Kill a Mockingbird. The methodology includes thematic analysis to identify and interpret the recurring appearances of the main characters throughout the narratives.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The settings, heroes, and symbolic icons of the two novels share numerous similarities. Arthur “Boo” Radley from To Kill a Mockingbird is paralleled in Jasper Jones as Jack Lionel. Boo Radley is an individual with a childish character who is misinterpreted by his society as a cruel monster, although this perception has no basis in reality. He is as vulnerable as a child or a teenager who seeks connection with children who initially attempt to tease him. After hearing numerous negative stories about him, the children become eager to meet and know him. As described in the novel:

“Jem gave a reasonable description of Boo: Boo was about six-and-a-half feet tall, judging from his tracks; he dined on raw squirrels and any cats he could catch, that’s why his hands were blood-stained—if you ate an animal raw, you could never wash the blood off. There was a long-jagged scar that ran across his face; what teeth he had were yellow and rotten; his eyes popped, and he drooled most of the time.” (Lee, 1960)

Similarly, Jack Lionel in Jasper Jones is an old, kind man who is mistakenly depicted as a murderer. Interestingly, as time passed, the stories about him were continuously embellished with new additions and alterations. Children were terrified to approach his house, which became a place of fascination. As described in the novel:

“A popular test, of course, in ething from the property of Mad Jack Lionel. Rocks and flowers and assorted debris are all rushed back proudly from the high dry-grass sprawl of his front yard to be examined with wonder.” (Silvey, 2009)

Furthermore, two additional characters resemble each other: Tom Robinson from To Kill a Mockingbird and Jasper Jones from Jasper Jones. Tom Robinson is a middle-aged African-American man who is married with children. He is a naive man with a pure heart who disregards the discrimination he has endured throughout his life as an African-American (Akhrorova, 2025-b). White people from the western part of America considered Black people as inferior, and without question, Black people were expected to serve white individuals. This entrenched racial inequality seemed momentarily suspended in Tom Robinson’s interaction with Mayella Ewell.

Unfortunately, he made a grave mistake by crossing that boundary and was ultimately accused of assaulting Mayella. The guilty verdict against Tom Robinson represented a profound injustice (Akhrova, 2025-a).

Similarly, Jasper Jones is described as follows:

“Jasper Jones has a terrible reputation in Corrigan. He’s a thief, a liar, a thug, a truant. He’s lazy and unreliable. He’s a feral and an orphan—or as good as. His mother is dead, and his father is no good. He’s the rotten model that parents hold aloft as a warning: This is how you’ll end up if you’re disobedient. Jasper Jones is an example of where poor aptitude and attitude will lead.” (Silvey, 2009)

He is the scapegoat of his society, blamed for every misfortune in the community, even though he is innocent. Simply because he is not white, he faces constant discrimination. Despite being a teenager, he is accused of every misdeed that occurs in his small town.

In *To Kill a Mockingbird*, Scout presents a childish perspective, discussing her reading ability before attending school and during her early school years. In contrast, Charlie demonstrates a strong passion for books and reading novels. The following quote from Jasper Jones reflects Charlie’s interest in Harper Lee’s work:

“I enjoyed the Harper Lee book the best...” (Silvey, 2009, p. 8)

Through the protagonist Charlie, Craig Silvey emphasizes the connection between the two novels, despite their differences. Although both novels feature victims of severe racism—Tom Robinson in *To Kill a Mockingbird* and Jasper Jones in *Jasper Jones*—their backgrounds, marital status, and ages differ. Tom Robinson is a strong, mature man with a wife and children who works daily, whereas Jasper Jones is a young teenager in love with his peer.

Moreover, Jasper Jones presents darker thematic elements, including domestic violence, child abuse, and suicide, often set against nighttime backdrops. In contrast, *To Kill a Mockingbird* portrays these themes in a milder form, though it too contains tragic elements. Domestic violence appears in *To Kill a Mockingbird* through Bob Ewell’s abusive relationship with his daughter. However, Laura Wishart in *Jasper Jones* endures severe emotional and physical abuse from her influential stepfather, who holds significant power in Corrigan. His authority was so strong that Laura’s mother attempted to conceal the only evidence—Laura’s final letter written before her death.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

By reading *Jasper Jones* in light of *To Kill a Mockingbird*, one may recognize that Harper Lee’s novel is a true classic masterpiece, playing a significant role in world literature, particularly influencing Craig Silvey’s narrative. The reflected influence on the modern novel *Jasper Jones* is evident through its portrayal of racial injustice, societal prejudice, and the loss of innocence experienced by the protagonists. As *Jasper Jones* is often regarded as a literary descendant of *To Kill a Mockingbird*, the two novels exhibit strong connections and similarities in tone, setting, and themes of racial discrimination, while also presenting considerable differences.

This article has analyzed the intertextual connection between the two novels by comparing the innocent characters who share similarities across both works.

Future research may expand this comparative analysis by exploring additional intertextual parallels between twentieth-century and twenty-first-century literature. Moreover, further investigation could examine how adaptations of classic narratives, such as *Jasper Jones*, serve as culturally specific reinterpretations of universal themes like injustice, prejudice, and moral growth. Such studies could contribute valuable insights into the evolution of coming-of-age literature across different historical and cultural contexts.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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